

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF VARIETAL SAMPLES OF CHILLI PEPPER GROWN UNDER GREENHOUSE CONDITIONS

Scientific-research institute of vegetables, melon crops and potatoes

Khushvaktov Nurbek Jumaevich, PhD on agr.sci.

Abstract

This article presents information on the results of phenological observations parameters and biometric measurements of chilli pepper cultivars with good fruit quality and high yield suitable for greenhouse cultivation. It took 2–5 days for viability and growth of 10% of the sown varietal samples, while for 75% of samples required 4–9 days. The viability and growth of Dilnoz 2019 cultivar seedlings was observed to require 2–3 days later than Margilon 330 cultivar planted in the control option, while the seedlings of Niyat cultivar (10–75%) flowered 2–8 days later than the control cultivar. It was observed that during mass flowering of chilli pepper varietal samples planted in greenhouse conditions, the plant height of Margilon 330 cultivar planted in the control option was 53.0 centimeters, while the height of Dilnoz 2019, Sharq gavhari cultivars was 15.5-30.2 percent higher than the control option.

Key words: chilli pepper, greenhouse, plant height, number of lateral branches, budding, flowering, fruiting, ripening of fruits, viability of seedlings.

Introduction. The largest producers of chilli pepper in the world are China, Vietnam, Mexico, Turkey, Nigeria, Spain, Indonesia, India and Brazil. Asia supplies 57 percent of the chilli pepper produced in the world, while Europe supplies 14.7 percent. In Spain, chilli pepper is grown on an area of 58,000 hectares mainly in heated and unheated greenhouses. Over the past ten years, the

area under chilli pepper cultivation has increased by 13 percent, including a doubling of chilli pepper production due to protected facilities to meet the population's demand for fresh product in the off-season. In most of the countries leading chilli pepper cultivation in greenhouses, extensive scientific research is being conducted on its productivity, product quality, and delivery of fresh products especially for the specified season.

Therefore, in order to expand the range of greenhouse vegetables, to meet the growing needs of our population for fresh products in the off-season, it is expedient to conduct research on the cultivation of chilli pepper in unheated greenhouse conditions.

Based on this goal, an important task was set to study thoroughly a collection of samples of chilli pepper varieties with a short growing season, with good spiciness and valuable content, and to select and introduce varieties suitable for the climatic conditions of our republic. Margilon 330, Uchkun (2009), Tillarang (2010) and Said (2015) cultivars of chilli pepper belonging to Asian type, have been included in the State Register of red peppers since 1950, and they have been adapted to local conditions of our country and are cultivated in open fields at present. Research on chilli pepper selection and cultivation technology was conducted in our Republic only for the conditions of open fields. Based on the needs of the population for fresh products in the off-season period of the year, the research on the selection of chilli pepper varieties suitable for planting in greenhouses, the study of its varietal breeding, the selection of promising varieties, and the improvement of cultivation technology is being conducted.

In the experiments, Margilon 330 cultivar, included in the state register of agricultural crops recommended for planting in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, was selected as a control variety. During the experiment were used 8

varietal samples created in Indonesia, 8 varietal samples created in South Korea, 1 varietal sample from the Netherlands, 5 varietal samples from Uzbekistan and 13 varietal samples from the gene pool of the Plant Genetic Resources Research Institute. The phenological parameters of chilli pepper cultivars samples grown in greenhouse conditions were studied (Table 1).

The purpose of the research is to select high-yield chilli pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.) varieties suitable for growing in greenhouses and to create high-yield varieties with good fruit quality.

Research methods. Greenhouse and laboratory research was carried out according to the guidelines and methodological manuals such as "Experimental methods in vegetable and melon growing", "Methodology of conducting experiments in vegetable, melon crops and potato growing", "Guidelines for studying and maintaining the world collection of vegetable nightshade crops (tomatoes, peppers, eggplants)", "Methodological recommendations for conducting experiments with vegetable crops in protected ground structures (RIVG)", and the statistical analysis of the results was carried out using the Microsoft Excel program in the dispersion analysis method of B.A.Dospekhov.

Great attention should be paid to planting seedlings in the greenhouse in early spring. In the cool weather of early spring, chilli pepper seedlings require sufficient heat to stay viable. In experiments, seedlings were planted on February 20. For the experiment, the seedlings with height of 15–20 cm were selected, the number of leaves per seedling was 6–8 pieces. When the seedlings were planted in the experimental area, 98% viability was recorded. It is a good indicator that seedlings can be viable and grow in this amount in the cool weather of early spring.

Table-1

Phenological parameters of varietal samples of chilli pepper planted in

greenhouse condition (in 2020–2023)

№	Varietal samples	Seedlings viability, day		From planting the seedlings, day					
				to mass flowering		to ripening		to mass ripening	
		10%	75%	10%	75%	10%	75%	10%	75%
1	Margilon 330 (control)	4	7	26	35	41	49	61	76
2 1	Dilnoz 2019	4	9	24	31	36	42	55	70
2 3	Sharq gavhari	3	8	27	34	40	45	58	69
2 5	Niyat	4	7	28	34	39	45	58	73

It is very important to study the development periods and the duration of the growth period of the variety samples studied in the greenhouse. It took 2–5 days for 10% viability of the sown varietal samples, while for 75% viability and growth of samples it required 4–9 days. The viability and growth of Dilnoz 2019 cultivar seedlings was observed to require 2–3 days later than Margilon 330 cultivar planted in the control option, while the seedlings of Niyat cultivar (10–75%) flowered 2–8 days later than the control cultivar.

Famous scientists such as Ye.Ya. Glushenko, M.V.Voronina, A.I. Strekalova in their literature divided the pepper plant into the following groups according to its height: short – up to 25 cm; short – up to 26–45 cm; medium height – 46–65 cm; high – 66–86 cm; very high – above 86 centimeters.

Table-3.4

Plant height and number of lateral shoots of chilli pepper cultivars grown

under unheated greenhouse conditions

(2018–2020)

№	Varietal samples	Mass flowering period				Mass fruit ripening period			
		Plant height		Number of lateral shoots		Plant height		Number of lateral shoots	
		cm	%	pcs	%	cm	%	pcs	%
1	Margilon 330 (st)	53,0	100,0	2,0	100,0	103,2	100,0	2,0	100,0
2 1	Dilnoz 2019	57,1	107,7	2,0	100,0	83,0	80,4	2,0	100,0
2 3	Sharq gavhari	67,1	126,6	2,0	100,0	125,3	121,4	2,0	100,0
2 5	Niyat	46,3	87,4	2,0	100,0	94,4	91,5	2,0	100,0

During the mass flowering period of chilli pepper variety samples planted in greenhouse conditions, the plant height was 53.0 centimeters in Margilon 330 variety planted in the control option, while it was observed that Dilnoz 2019, Sharq gavhari varieties showed 15.5-30.2% higher indicators for height than the control option.

Based on the information of Ye.Ya. Glushenko, M. V. Voronina, A.I. Strekalova, when the height of the plant was determined in the period of mass flowering of chilli pepper variety samples, Dilnoz 2019 and Niyat cultivars (46.3–63 cm) were included in the medium-sized group, Sharq gavhari cultivar was (67–69 cm) included in high height group of chilli pepper varieties.

REFERENCES USED

1. DeWitt, D., and Bosland, P. W. Complete Chile Pepper Book: A Gardener's Guide to Choosing, Growing, Preserving, and Cooking. Timber Press. (2009). P // 3389–3396.
2. Gikalo G.S. Regionized chilli pepper cultivars./ Cultivation of pepper and eggplant in Krasnodar region.- Kn.publ.house, 1972. P. 60–63.
3. Description of varieties included in the state register of agricultural crops recommended for planting on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2010. P. 51-52.
4. Mamedov M.I., Pyshnaya O.N. Selection of chilli pepper for fruit quality . // The collec.sci.theor.conf. “Selection and seed-breeding of vegetable crops” M., 1998. P.127.